

104. Light deflection... by Jupiter

IN GENERAL RELATIVITY, the presence of matter (energy density) distorts spacetime, and the path of electromagnetic radiation is deflected as a result.

Formally, the equations of light propagation are derived from the general relativistic Maxwell equations. For the solar system, they can also be derived in the limit of geometrical optics since wavelength-dependent relativistic effects are much smaller than 1 microarcsec.

For a spherically symmetric gravitational field, the general expression for the deflection angle reduces to the ‘post-Newtonian’ formula $\delta\chi = \frac{2GM}{bc^2} \frac{(1+\gamma)}{2} \cot(\chi/2)$, where G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the deflecting body, b is the impact parameter, c is the velocity of light, and χ the angular separation between the deflecting body and the source.

Inclusion of the term γ , which appears in the so-called Parameterised Post-Newtonian (PPN) approximation (relevant for the slow-motion, weak-field limit), is convenient for comparing ‘metric’ theories of gravity and, in particular, assessing how well general relativity matches specific experimental tests. In general relativity $\gamma = 1$, while the classical derivation of light bending yields only the first part of the leading coefficient in this expression, viz. the factor 1/2. Conventionally, experimental results are expressed in terms of $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma)$.

For grazing incidence at the solar limb, the expression reduces to $\delta\chi \approx \frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) 1.7505$ arcsec. In other words, with $\gamma = 1$, stars observed close to the solar limb are deflected by an angle of 1.7 arcsec.

LIGHT DEFLECTION has been observed, with various degrees of precision, on distance scales of $10^9 - 10^{21}$ m, and on mass scales from $10^{-3} - 10^{13} M_{\odot}$, the lower range from planetary deflection at 200 arcsec from Jupiter (Treuhaft & Lowe, 1991), and the upper range from the lensing of quasars (originally Dar, 1992).

Observational confirmation based on the 1919 solar eclipse in Brazil (Dyson et al., 1920) was of limited accuracy, while the most recent *ground-based* astrometric solar eclipse campaign, from Chinguetti (Mauritania) in 1973, yielded $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) = 0.95 \pm 0.10$ (Jones, 1976).

Light deflection from the 1973 total solar eclipse at Chinguetti

THE DEVELOPMENT of radio interferometry and radio VLBI greatly improved the measurement of light deflection: a 1995 VLBI measurement of 3C 273 and 3C 279 yielded $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) = 0.9996 \pm 0.0017$ (Lebach et al., 1995), and a later analysis of nearly 2 million VLBI observations of 541 radio sources from 87 VLBI sites yielded $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) = 0.99992 \pm 0.00023$ (Shapiro et al., 2004). And Fomalont & Kopeikin (2003) reported VLBA–Effelsberg observations of ‘light’ bending of the quasar J0842+1835 at 3.7 arcmin from Jupiter.

THAT THE EFFECT of relativistic light bending had to be accounted for in the Hipparcos data analysis is evident from the magnitude of the effect. As noted above, according to general relativity, light bending at the solar limb reaches 1.75 arcsec. But given the Hipparcos measurement accuracies, the effect remains significant over almost the entire celestial sphere, amounting to about 4 milli-arcsec even at 90° from the Sun, i.e. for star light arriving orthogonal to the ecliptic.

The approach adopted for Hipparcos was to introduce the predicted light bending, at each measurement epoch, as fully deterministic as far as effects due to the Sun (and the Earth in the case of the NDAC consortium) were considered.

The measurements were then assessed for systematic departures from the prescriptions of general relativity, with the objective of assessing whether general relativity provides an adequate framework, or whether an alternative theory of gravity is indicated. The detailed analysis of the Hipparcos great-circle abscissae residuals gave $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \gamma) = 0.9985 \pm 0.0015$ (Froeschlé et al., 1997).

ALTHOUGH THE Hipparcos accuracy was improved upon by VLBI, it is noteworthy that the former was derived from observations at large solar angles, i.e. not constrained to within a few solar radii, and with a single instrument. And while the same framework applies equally to Gaia, the geometrical model for Hipparcos (at the level of 1 milli-arcsec) required major refinements in the case of Gaia (at around 1 micro-arcsec).

The adopted model, formulated within the Barycentric Celestial Reference System (BCRS), actually comprises five successive transformations (Klioner, 2003). Indeed, parallax and proper motion are no longer effects which can be considered separately, or independently, of the chosen coordinate-dependent model.

A FURTHER complication when considering light bending, whether by the Sun, Earth, or the other planets, is that they are not spherical, but rather (due to rotation) better approximated as oblate spheroids.

Their resulting gravitational potential can be written as the expansion $U = -GM(C_0 r^{-1} + C_1 r^{-2} + C_2 r^{-3} \dots)$, thus defining the monopole moment (C_0), the dipole moment (C_1), the quadrupole moment (C_2), and so on.

For the Sun and Jupiter, the monopole terms at grazing incidence are 1.7 arcsec and 16.27 milli-arcsec respectively. But while the quadrupole term at grazing incidence is only around 1 micro-arcsec for the Sun, it is a significant 240 micro-arcsec for Jupiter (Klioner, 2003; Ludl, 2011).

A final caveat is that the geometry of light deflection is similar to that of the parallax displacement, although differing in direction and in their dependence on χ : varying as $\cot(\chi/2)$ for light bending, and as $\pi \sin \chi$ for parallax. This allows the two distinct effects to be separated in the observation equations, although they remain highly correlated.

In summary, light deflection measurements to date have succeeded in confirming the monopole light deflection predicted by general relativity. The quadrupole light deflection term has not yet been measured.

THE POSSIBILITY of making these tests was highlighted in the ESA Gaia Phase A report (2000), with an expected precision of about 5×10^{-7} for γ , based on multiple observations of $\sim 10^7$ stars with $V < 13$ mag.

Gaia's scanning law means that, while $\chi_{\min} = 45^\circ$ for the Sun, scans very close to grazing incidence are possible for Jupiter, albeit complicated by the effects of scattered light. Nonetheless, the observation of stars with very small impact parameters are required, because while light-bending due to the monopole moment falls off as r^{-2} , that of the dipole falls off as r^{-3} .

WHILE IT IS too early to have any insight into Gaia results for light-bending by the Sun, observations of stars close to Jupiter's limb have recently been reported using star positions from Gaia DR3 (Abbas et al., 2022).

But we should first go back to a time just after the launch of Gaia in 2013, when a study of the optimum precession and spin phases of the 'scanning law' was made by Klioner & Mignard (2014). They took into account the predicted configuration of three stars with $G < 15.75$ close to Jupiter's limb (within 6 Jupiter radii) which would take place between 22–26 February 2017.

These high-cadence observations were duly obtained, with the closest of the three observed at just 7 arcsec from Jupiter's limb. The closest bright star, with $G = 12.78$ mag, was observed on 25 almost consecutive transits spread over a few days.

The analysis, based on differential measurements, required the consideration of scattered light, differential aberration of several milli-arcsec along-scan, differential proper motions of order tens of micro-arcsec over 24 hours, and the non-linear differential light deflection, actually dominated by Jupiter's monopole.

The measured deflection, of around 10 milli-arcsec, represented the combined effect of Jupiter and the Sun (projected in the along-scan direction), and is mainly dominated by Jupiter's monopole. It was detected with a signal-to-noise of 50 at closest approach. It is the closest measurement made to Jupiter's limb in the optical, the highest signal-to-noise at any wavelength, and again provides excellent agreement between the Gaia observations and the predictions of general relativity.

Light deflection due to Jupiter, measured by Gaia

IT SETS THE STAGE for future efforts to disentangle an along-scan component of some 100 micro-arcsec at closest approach due to Jupiter's quadrupole moment from the much larger monopole deflection of around 10 milli-arcsec. And with Data Release 3 covering data only up to May 2017, two similar events, predicted to occur during September 2018 and April 2019, should be available in future data releases.